

PUBLICATION 1

Article title: How green are full open-access publications in Translation Studies journals? A corpus study.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the fields of Translation Studies and scholarly publishing have witnessed significant transformations, not least through the expansion of open access journals and the growing prominence of ethical inquiry within the applied linguistics discipline. Yet, strikingly little attention has been paid to questions of environmental sustainability and the escalating climate crisis, despite their profound global implications. This relative absence is increasingly difficult to justify in light of the intensifying climate emergency, alongside the rapid proliferation of artificial intelligence technologies whose substantial energy demands carry their own environmental costs. At the same time, the discipline's expanding engagement with ethics (i.e. responsibility, agency, the social impact of translation) offers a compelling framework within which ecological concerns could, and arguably should, be more fully integrated. Surfacing the scarcity of focused publications in the area of Translation Studies and addressing this gap is therefore both timely and necessary.

In order to study the presence (or absence) of references to environmental issues in Translation Studies academic journals, a collaboration was established between the FASCA project and individual researcher Patricia Rodríguez-Inés, from the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Such collaboration project was called GREANISSH, which stands for GoTriple for Raising Environmental Awareness in Social Sciences and Humanities.

To understand how the collaboration between the FASCA project and an individual researcher was enabled, a brief explanation of how various relevant entities are linked must be offered. OPERAS is the umbrella infrastructure for the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) in Europe which provides the organisational framework, services, resource federation, visibility, and Open Science policies. GoTriple is a service hosted within the OPERAS ecosystem which was developed (by the TRIPLE project) and is operated by OPERAS to provide a multilingual discovery service for SSH resources. FASCA is a project that uses GoTriple (and therefore the OPERAS infrastructure) to offer advanced scholarly communication analysis, linked to FAIR outputs, SDGs, data, and

code. In April 2025 GoTriple Data Services invited researchers in the Social Sciences and Humanities to participate in an open call for pilot projects, which ended up with GREANISSH being one of the two selected projects to start in September 2025.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

In spite of the rising interest on the intersection between Translation Studies and Ecology, there are still very few long and focused works to be cited. One of them is Hu Gengshen's *Eco-Translatology: Construction & Interpretation* (2013), which develops a theoretical framework that views translation as an adaptive process shaped by ecological principles, where translators negotiate and select strategies in response to linguistic, cultural, and communicative environments. The book foregrounds the idea of "adaptation and selection" as the core mechanism of translation, emphasising the dynamic interaction between translators and their broader eco-environment. Another seminal work is Michael Cronin's *Eco-Translation: Translation and Ecology in the Age of the Anthropocene* (2017), which examines how the concept of the anthropocene reshapes our understanding of translation by positioning it as a socially and environmentally embedded practice, deeply implicated in global ecological challenges. It argues that translation is not, as we know, merely linguistic transfer but a critical activity that mediates relationships between human and non-human worlds, foregrounding issues such as sustainability, cultural diversity, and the ethical responsibilities of translators in the context of climate change. More recent publications are *Eco-Translatology: Towards an Eco-paradigm of Translation Studies* (Hu, 2020), which is the author's further development of his previous work, and Dasca and Cerarols' (2024) edited volume *Translation Studies and Ecology: Mapping the Possibilities of a New Emerging Field*, with contributions about postcolonialism, ecofeminism, linguistic variation or animal studies. A relevant and promising forthcoming publication is *Routledge's Handbook of Translation and Sustainability*, edited by Lambert, Giustini and Gaspari, with a dedicated part on ecological sustainability, and more specifically, on the environmental impact of translation and interpreting technologies, eco-translation, the climate crisis, and natural resources.

METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The GREANISSH project has meant that an SSH researcher has been able to work with a complete pipeline: from discovery (using GoTriple resources) to

data-driven analysis (supported by FASCA project members), all within an infrastructure (OPERAS) that actually participates in a higher-level European Open Science framework (OSCARS).

More specifically, FASCA project members from the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences provided the individual researcher with expert technical support on the research design and its implementation, document and metadata harvesting, and the exploitation of results.

Corpus design criteria:

Academic texts extracted from full open-access Translation Studies journals indexed in either or several of these quality indexes: AHCI, SSCI, ESCI, SCOPUS, ERIH PLUS, JCR, SJR, CARHUS PLUS, FECYT, and which contain the lemma "translation" in the title of the journal, in any language. The starting point to identify the journals was the database [RETI: Journals of Translation and Interpreting Studies. Open Access](#). Also, as a design feature, the targeted journal websites had to be based on the OAI-PMH protocol to facilitate the harvesting of metadata.

Document and metadata harvesting:

To collect metadata, the websites of journals from a previously prepared list were analyzed in order to identify available OAI-PMH endpoints. To ensure data consistency and simplify the aggregation process, only endpoints providing metadata in the Dublin Core (oai_dc) format were used. As a result, 20 active endpoints meeting these criteria were identified.

The metadata harvesting process was carried out using Python, with dedicated computational notebooks (.ipynb) prepared for this purpose. The Sickie¹ library was used to handle the OAI-PMH protocol, while tqdm² and pandas³ were used for progress monitoring and data processing.

In the next stage, a procedure for downloading full-text publications in PDF format was developed in order to build a research corpus. For this purpose, links contained in the 'relation' field of the metadata were utilized. This process was implemented using Python's standard libraries as well as external modules including requests⁴, pandas, and tqdm.

Subsequently, a set of basic statistics describing the collected dataset was prepared. These included, among others, the number of keywords, the number of authors, the distribution of authors per publication, the distribution of

¹ Source repository: <https://github.com/mloesch/sickle>

² Source repository: <https://github.com/tqdm/tqdm>

³ Source repository: <https://github.com/pandas-dev/pandas>

⁴ Source repository: <https://github.com/psf/requests>

publication languages, and the temporal distribution of records. To improve the quality of the analysis, preliminary data cleaning and normalization steps were performed. These included removing affiliation information from author fields, eliminating journal names and editorial board information incorrectly assigned to the author field, standardizing language codes, and translating keywords into English using automatic translation. The translation was performed using the deep-translator⁵ library.

The resulting dataset, consisting of metadata, full texts, and computed statistics, was then forwarded for further analysis.

The source code used to perform the above processes is available in the repository: <https://github.com/nwolczuk/fasca-pilot-1>.

The data generated as a result of these activities have been deposited in the Zenodo repository: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19731882>.

Full corpus description:

- Number of journals: 20⁶
- Number of documents: 9368 pdf files
- Document year range: January 1996 – October 2025 (30 years)

Analysis procedure

After harvesting the metadata from the 9000+ publications, these metadata were merged into a single spreadsheet to which filters were applied. Text filters using truncated words or lemmas were found to be the most efficient way of identifying publications that dealt with environmental issues. The searches that proved most productive to obtain results in different languages were: eco*, climat*, environment*, sustainab*, ambient*, and sostenib*.

Given the very limited number of results, the analysis was rather qualitative than quantitative, although some figures have been provided for description purposes.

In order to complement the few results obtained from the Translation Studies corpus, the GoTriple search platform was used to expand the analysis to the field of Linguistics in general. The only search string *translation AND (climate OR ecology OR environmental)* already yielded more than 100 relevant results, most of them articles from non-mainstream journals, PhD theses, etc.

⁵ Source repository: <https://github.com/nidhaloff/deep-translator>

⁶ *Cadernos de Tradução, Clina, Estudios de Traducción, Hermeneus, Hikma, Journal of Specialized Translation, Lingüística Antverpiensia, Multicultural Shakespeare, New Voices in Translation Studies, Onomázein, Quaderns de Traducció, Rocznik, Sendebär, Ticontre, Tradumàtica, Trans, Transfer, Translation Matters, Viceversa.*

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- There are only 29 publications where environmental sustainability or climate-related words are included either in the title or in the keywords of the 9000+ document corpus.
- Language breakdown:
 - ES = 14 publications
 - EN = 11
 - PT = 2
 - CA = 1
 - IT = 1
- Publication type breakdown:
 - Articles = 24
 - Book reviews = 2
 - Interviews = 1
 - Videos = 1
 - PhD thesis abstracts = 1
- Year of publication breakdown:
 - 2001 = 1 publication
 - 2009 = 1
 - 2012 = 1
 - 2013 = 1
 - 2017 = 1
 - 2018 = 1
 - 2020 = 2
 - 2021 = 2
 - 2022 = 4
 - 2023 = 4
 - 2024 = 6
 - 2025 = 3

The frequency data clearly show that environmental issues remain marginal within Translation Studies, having received very limited scholarly attention to date. Out of a corpus of more than 9,000 academic publications, only 29 include references to environmental sustainability or climate-related topics in their titles or keywords, confirming the peripheral status of this research area. In spite of this, it must be acknowledged that most publications (19) include topic-relevant words both in the title and as keywords, meaning that, once the topic is dealt with, it is usually central to the publication. The language distribution reveals a slight predominance of Spanish (14 publications), followed by English (11), with

only isolated contributions in Portuguese, Catalan, and Italian, suggesting that interest is both geographically and linguistically uneven. The imbalance towards publications in Spanish is explained by the fact that 11 out of the 20 journals are edited and produced in Spanish-speaking countries, which speaks well about their commitment towards open-access publishing and easy data sharing (OAI-PMH protocol enabled). In terms of publication types, the overwhelming majority are research articles (24), with minimal representation of other formats. Most authors are one-timers, with the exception of González Vallejo (2022, 2023, 2024), Montero-Martínez (2022, 2025) and Moorkens et al. (2024, which speaks about the same publication in two different formats). The journal that has published the largest number of articles on the topic is *Cadernos de Tradução*, with four papers (Gohn 2001, Zhang & Lou 2023, González Vallejo 2024, Fois and Milia 2025). Chronologically, the data point to a very recent emergence of the topic: although sporadic publications appear as early as 2001 (Gohn), there is a noticeable increase only from 2020 onwards, peaking in 2024. Overall, these patterns suggest that while interest in environmental concerns within Translation Studies is beginning to grow, it is still in an early and underdeveloped stage.

Search results from the merged metadata file (9435 entries):

SEARCH STRING	EXACT WORD FOUND IN METADATA SECTION: TITLE	EXACT WORD FOUND IN METADATA SECTION: KEYWORDS = "SUBJECT"	DOCUMENT TYPE (ARTICLE/ REVIEW/ ABSTRACT/ INTRO/ VIDEO/ INTERVIEW)	YEAR	LANGUAGE	JOURNAL
Eco	teoria de l'ecotraducció	ecotraducció	article	2022	CA	Quaderns (25)
	perspectiva da eco-translatologia	eco-translatologia	article	2023	PT	Cadernos (8)
	eco-Translatology		review	2018	ES	Hermeneus (10)
	eco-Translation + ecology		review	2023	EN	New Voices (16)
	ecology	language of ecology	thesis abstract	2023	EN	New Voices (16)
	ecological turn		article	2022	EN	Translation matters (18)
	ecopoesía	ecopoesía	interview	2023	ES	Viceversa (39)
	recurso ecolingüístico digital	ecologías del aprendizaje	article	2024	ES	Quaderns (25)
	ecolinguistics	ecotranslation, ecolinguistics	article	2025	EN	Cadernos (8)
	EcoLexicon	terminología medioambiental, contaminación atmosférica, gestión de residuos, EcoLexicon	article	2025	ES	Hermeneus (10)
	ecocrítica	ecocrítica, biorregionalismo, medio ambiente	article	2012	ES	Sendebarr (11)
	ecoalfabetización	ecoalfabetización, ecotraducción, lenguaje del medioambiente	article	2022	ES	Trans (13)
	ecoliteracy		article	2021	EN	Translation matters (18)
	EcoLexicon		article	2013	EN	Jostrans (1)
	ecobiografía	ecobiografía, ecopoética	article	2025	IT	Ticontre (30)
	ecocrítica	ecología cultural, ecocrítica	article	2021	ES	Transfer (31)
	EcoLexicon	terminología medioambiental, EcoLexicon	article	2020	ES	Onomazein (3)
	ecocritical	ecocriticism, trees, woods, forest	article	2020	EN	Multicultural Shakespeare (5)
		eco-translation	article	2024	EN	New Voices (16)
		ecología de la cultura	article	2009	ES	Hikma (22)

		ecología	article	2017	ES	Transfer (31)
		ecocriticism	article	2024	EN	Multicultural Shakespeare (5)
Climat	cambio climático	cambio climático	article	2022	ES	Hermeneus (10)
Environment	environmental critical discourse analysis	environmental discourse	article	2025	EN	Onomazein (3)
ambient	preservação do meio ambiente		article	2001	PT	Cadernos (8)
	medioambiente	lenguaje ambiental	miscelanea	2023	ES	Estudios de T (28)
	textos técnicos medioambientales + informe de auditoría ambiental	medioambiente, informe de auditoría ambiental	article	2024	ES	Cadernos (8)
Sostenib	turismo sostenible	turismo sostenible	article	2022	ES	Estudios de T (28)
Sustainab	sustainability	sustainability	introduction	2024	EN	Jostrans (1)
	sustainability		video (roundtable)	2024	EN	Jostrans (1)
Planet / earth / green /	0	0				
Sostenib / sustainab		0				
eko	0	0				
klimat	0	0				

Regarding the interpretation of the words both from titles and keywords included in the table above, the list suggests a strong clustering of academic titles around the prefix *eco-* as a productive lemma, signalling a clear ecological orientation among the very few identified publications. Specifically, key clusters such as *eco-translation* and *eco-translatology* suggest a growing subfield linking translation studies and ecological thought. *Ecocriticism* appears to be among the most frequent concepts referred to in titles and keywords, followed by the specific mention of the terminological resource *EcoLexicon*, and the concepts of *ecoliteracy* and *ecopoetry*, which may point to the extension of ecological concerns into language, education, and literary studies. Likewise, *ecology-based* words (including *cultural ecology*, *ecology of culture*, *ecologies of learning* and *ecological turn*) reinforce the idea of intersections between Translation Studies and other fields. Another major grouping revolves around the *environment-* lemma (e.g. *environment*, *environmental discourse*, *environmental terminology*, *environmental audit report*), highlighting both conceptual and applied dimensions, particularly in technical and professional contexts. Overall, this analysis suggests that, although the number of translation publications on environmental topics in full open-access journals has been extremely low over the past 30 years, the few that do exist demonstrate a commitment to the subject and a variety of specific foci.

CONCLUSIONS

- Related to content: clear lack of interest in/attention to environmental issues in Translation Studies
- Related to journals' profile: majority of Spanish journals – (bias in selection criteria?)
- Related to open-access: need to promote implementation of OAI-PMH protocol to facilitate metadata sharing